

Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Silver(I) with 4-S-Benzyl-1-*p*-Chlorophenyl-5-Phenyl-2,4-Isodithiobiuret (BPPTB)

B. K. DESHMUKH

Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University, Nagpur-440 010

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4-S-Benzyl-1-*par*achlorophenyl-5-phenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (BPPTB) was used for the quantitative extraction of silver at trace level. Silver was extracted quantitatively at pH 6.1-7.7 with 0.002 *M* BPPTB in chloroform. The solution exhibits peak of maximum absorption at 500 nm. The system followed Beer's law in the concentration range of 1.1 to 21.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of silver. The complex was stable for 2 hr. 10 ml of 0.002 *M* BPPTB in chloroform was sufficient for quantitative extraction of silver. The optimum period of agitation was 5 min. It was possible to achieve extractive separation and colorimetric determination of silver in the presence of a large number of cations and anions.

4-S-BENZYL-1-*par*achlorophenyl-5-phenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (BPPTB) has been used for extraction of Pd(II), Pt(II), Rh(III) and Cu(II)¹⁻⁴. These elements have been separated and estimated using spectrophotometric technique. The simultaneous spectrophotometric determination of these metals using BPPTB have also been reported⁵. The solid complexes of some transition metal complexes have been isolated and studied⁶. In the present paper the use of BPPTB for extractive separation of silver from various cations has been discussed.

Several chelating agents have been reported for the extraction of silver but only dithiozone, oxine, cupral and diluted tributyl phosphate were found to be effective for its separation at microgram levels^{7,8}. The ion-association complex of silver with salicylic acid and dibutylamine has been extracted with isobutyl methylketone⁹ but the ternary complex with *o*-phenanthroline-bromopyrogallol red¹⁰ proved to be the most useful for selective extraction. Bis(2-ethylhexyl)phosphoric acid (HDEHP)¹¹ and diethyldithiophosphoric acid¹² have also been used as extractants, but only inefficiently, for the extraction of silver. Silver has also been extracted by thiodibenzoylmethane¹³.

The proposed method is simple, rapid and affords clear-cut separation of silver at trace level from large number of ions.

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents: Beckman model DU-2 spectrophotometer with 10 mm light path quartz cells, ELICO pH-meter model LI-LOT, to and fro action flask shaker were used in this study.

4-S-Benzyl-1-*par*achlorophenyl-5-phenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (BPPTB) was synthesized as reported earlier¹. About 0.002 *M* BPPTB in chloroform was used. The fresh solution of reagent was used.

About 0.001 *M* solution of silver nitrate (AnalaR, B. D. H.) was used and standardized volumetrically¹⁴. The dilute solution containing 54 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of silver was prepared from stock solution by suitable dilution. The solution was stored in dark and standardized regularly.

General procedure: An aliquot of the solution containing 54 μg of silver was taken. After addition of 10-15 ml of water the pH of the solution was adjusted to 6.1-7.7 on a pH-meter using sodium acetate (0.1 *M*) and acetic acid (0.1 *M*). The volume of the aqueous phase was made upto 25 ml. The solution was then transferred to a separating funnel after addition of 10 ml 0.002 *M* BPPTB in chloroform and shaken on a flask shaker for about 5 min. The layers were allowed to separate, the separation being enhanced with the addition of borax buffer of pH 12.0. The aqueous phase was removed and the organic phase was measured at 500 nm against a reagent blank prepared similarly. The amount of silver extracted was computed from the calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra: The absorption spectra of silver-BPPTB complex ($\text{Ag} = 5.0 \times 10^{-6}$ *M*) against the reagent blank was taken. It is observed that the complex exhibits maximum absorbance at 500 nm. Hence all absorption measurements were taken at 500 nm. The molar absorptivity at 500 nm is 1.12×10^4 . The Sandell's sensitivity¹⁵ is 0.0096 $\mu\text{g/cm}^2$ at 500 nm.

Extraction as a function of pH: The extraction of silver was carried out at pH from 3-12 with BPPTB-chloroform. The results show that the extraction commenced at about pH 5.0 and was quantitative in the pH region of 6.1-7.7. The extraction was incomplete below and above these pH. Thus, the optimum pH for extraction is 6.1-7.7.

Beer's law : Different amounts of silver, ranging from 11 to 215 μg of silver per 10 ml of solution, were taken. They were extracted at pH 6.3 with 10 ml of 0.002 M BPPTB in chloroform. The absorbance of the complex was measured at 500 nm against the reagent as a blank. It was noted that the system adhered to Beer's law in the concentration limit of 1.1 to 21.5 μg of silver per ml at 500 nm.

Effect of BPPTB concentration : The silver was extracted at pH 6.3 with varying volumes and varying concentrations of the reagent. The results show that 10 ml of 0.002 M BPPTB was sufficient for quantitative extraction of silver. The extraction was incomplete at lower concentration of reagent. At higher concentrations of the reagent there was no increase in the absorption. Thus, the optimum reagent concentration is 0.002 M.

Stability of the colour of the complex : The absorption of the colour of the complex was measured at elapsed intervals of 0, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0 and 8.0 hr. It was observed that the complex was stable only for 2 hr. Light affects the stability of colour. The extract stored in dark is stable for 4 hr.

Period of agitation : Varying the equilibration period from 1.0 to 15 min revealed that extraction is quantitative within 2 min of agitation. The extraction time of 5 min was arbitrarily chosen for further studies.

Effect of foreign ions : The effect of several ions on the extraction behaviour of silver was studied. The tolerance was set at an amount needed to cause $\pm 2\%$ error in the recovery of silver. The results show that hundred times excess of Pb(II), Tl(III), Bi(III), Sb(III), As(III), Fe(III), phosphate, ascorbate and EDTA⁴⁻, twenty times excess of Ru(III), Rh(III), Pt(IV), Ir(III), Th(IV), Ce(IV) and ten times excess of Au(III) and fluoride did not interfere in the extraction and determination of 54 μg silver at pH 6.3 with 10 ml 0.002 M BPPTB in chloroform. It was also observed that silver could be separated from the five times excess Re(VI), two times excess molybdate and equal amount of Hg(II), Zn(II) and Mn(II) by this method. Pd(II) and Ni(II) in half excess could be tolerated whereas Cu(II) and Co(II) interfered seriously.

Effect of solvents : Various solvents were tried to study the effect of solvents on extraction of silver with BPPTB. It was observed that clear-cut separation and quantitative extraction took place with chloroform and benzene.

The absorbance of the solution for 54 μg silver from 15 determinations is found to be 0.560 ± 0.010 . The relative standard deviation is $\pm 1.2\%$. The method is applicable at trace concentrations of silver. It is possible to accomplish clear-cut separation of silver from various ions such as gold, lead, rhodium, ruthenium, platinum, iridium, lead, mercury and zinc with which it is usually associated. The method is rapid as the total time of separation is less than 30 min.

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References

1. B. K. DESHMUKH and R. B. KHARAT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 980.
2. B. K. DESHMUKH and R. B. KHARAT, *Microchem. J.*, 1979, **24**, 850.
3. B. K. DESHMUKH and R. B. KHARAT, *Microchem. J.* (in press).
4. B. K. DESHMUKH and R. B. KHARAT, *Fertiliser Technology*, 1980, **17**, 202.
5. B. K. DESHMUKH and R. B. KHARAT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 181.
6. N. S. BHAVE, Physicochemical Studies of Some Transition Metal Complexes, Ph.D. Thesis, Nagpur University, Nagpur, 1980.
7. A. K. DE, S. M. KHOPKAR and R. A. CHALMERS, "Solvent Extraction of Metals", Van Nostrand Reinhold, London, 1970.
8. A. K. YADAV and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1971, 464.
9. D. BETTERIDGE and T. S. WEST, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1962, **26**, 101.
10. R. M. DAGNALL and T. S. WEST, *Talanta*, 1964, **11**, 1627.
11. E. E. CRISS and Z. A. SHEKA, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1962, **7**, 658.
12. H. BODE and A. W. Z. ARNSWALD, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1962, **185**, 179.
13. R. R. MULYÉ and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1975, **76**, 204.
14. A. I. VOGEL, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", ELBS, London, 1975.
15. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", Interscience, New York, 1969.